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About the Organization

LESLLA aims to support adults who are learning to read and write for the first time in their lives in a new language. We promote, on a worldwide, multidisciplinary basis, the sharing of research findings, effective pedagogical practices, and information on policy.

LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

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Building the Letter-Sentence Bridge: Approaches to Teaching Early Literacy to LESLLA Adults

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This paper is an extension of a six-hour professional development training for adult ESL instructors, originally developed by Shelley Lee and taught by both of the authors.

When we first started teaching ESL over 15 years ago, the student population was much different than it is today. In the early 2000s, most students were Spanish-speaking immigrants seeking employment in the United States. The community college classes on life and work skills met their needs at the time. Starting in 2008, the number of LESLLA (Low Educated Second Language and Literacy Acquisition) students in our ESL classrooms increased, and we realized that some of our traditional methods of teaching ESL were becoming less and less effective. LESLLA learners were not benefiting as quickly from the mainstream ESL classes as other, more educated students who were familiar with Western-style education and the Roman alphabet. At the same time, many of our fellow ESL instructors were not prepared to teach LESLLA students. Oftentimes LESLLA students would drop out of beginner classes, usually because they were designed for students who already had literacy skills in their first language. LESLLA students struggled to learn to read in English and quickly fell behind their classmates. It is because of these disparities and the desire to include all students that we began to adjust our focus in the classroom.

Our classes are held at a community college in Raleigh, North Carolina, which, like many places in the U.S., has become home to a growing number of immigrants and refugees. Shelley taught for five years at the New Arrival School, designed especially for non- and semi-literate refugees. Her experiences working with newly-arrived, low-literacy adults served as a springboard for developing a new curriculum that brings explicit literacy instruction into the ESL classroom. Jaimie taught traditional ESL classes at both a non-profit and the local community college. When both organizations began to see an increasing number of LESLLA students, creating a new combined class of varying literacy levels, explicit phonics instruction became necessary for all students to participate actively in class. Both authors note that since significantly changing our approach to include systematic literacy instruction, we have noticed rapid growth among *all* students in class, not just LESLLA students. Our goal is to integrate the best ESL practices into literacy instruction and the best literacy practices into ESL instruction so that all students, LESLLA and traditional ESL students alike, can receive equal access to language and literacy acquisition.

Here, we summarize current research in ESL literacy instruction, note the guiding principles we use in class, and describe in detail some of the teaching techniques we use. The lessons included, can be used in classes made up entirely of LESLLA students, or in combined classes. Usually, we focus on direct literacy instruction for 45-60 minutes of each three-hour class and dedicate the rest of the time to ESL life skills, speaking, and listening. Individual teachers can determine the timing that works in his or her own classroom.

Research Base for Balanced Literacy Instruction

The debate about whole-language and phonics instruction seems to be over, as research increasingly supports a balanced literacy approach when working with beginning readers (Vinogradov, 2008, 2009). The core components of reading include phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension (National Reading Panel, 2000), but many LESLLA students have limited decoding skills and are not able to advance to the last, and most important, stage of understanding what they read.

To quickly summarize the two schools of thought, the whole-language/top-down approach focuses on *meaning*, while the traditional phonics/bottom-up approach mainly offers decontextualized acquisition of *letters and sounds*. While both have their place in the classroom, teachers cannot expect their students to pick up one without the other. All ESL students need to learn English within a context (Florez and Terrill, 2003), but

LESLLA students need context and more. As Wrigley (2003) states, “Mere exposure and continued acquisition of English” is not enough for LESLLA students to pick up literacy, just as only learning letter sounds and shapes cannot give students a full understanding of English. Rather, emergent readers need a balance of both methods, so that instruction is “both meaning-based and explicit” (Vinogradov, 2008).

When phonics instruction is contextualized, using both top-down and bottom-up approaches, the students’ needs are better met. For example, instructors can work on sounds and spelling patterns during a vocabulary lesson about a certain topic, allowing students to receive phonics instruction within a meaningful context. Literacy and language are intrinsically connected, and the teacher should provide opportunities for students to practice each one.

Guiding Principles

Guided by the research, our teaching style is motivated by these principles:

Progression from oral language to print (Vinogradov & Bigelow, 2010): Speaking practice comes before literacy skills. Students need to be able to say and understand the words before they can read them.

Daily, systematic instruction in foundational literacy: During each class, students should be exposed to the components of early literacy: print concepts, phonemic awareness, phonics, letter formation, and blending sounds into words.

Contextualized instruction: Learning to read doesn’t occur in a vacuum. Teachers should use engaging topics that capture students’ attention as a catalyst for phonemic instruction (Vinogradov, 2008).

Opportunity mindset: When teachers offer their students an opportunity for literacy (Gunn, 2003) instead of communicating a deficiency mindset, the students’ affective filter (Krashen, 1982) is lowered. Students feel more confident when they see that their teacher believes in their ability to learn.

Variety of practice activities: Having a balance between routine and variety (Wrigley, 2003) keeps the class interesting and the students motivated. Andrea Echelberger, in the New American Horizons video series, exemplifies this practice with her LESLLA learners.

In the sections that follow, we describe personal classroom-tested lessons that reflect our guiding principles and help students move from letter-sound recognition to reading whole sentences.

Literacy Lessons

I. Letter-Sound Connection.

In order to learn the building blocks of the Roman alphabet, LESLLA students need explicit instruction in phonemic awareness and English phonics. Many teachers give LESLLA students the whole alphabet at once and teach the letter names but not the letter sounds. This approach is not the best one for LESLLA students (Vinogradov, 2008), as it is more effective to focus on a few letters and sounds at a time, teaching each of them to mastery. This lesson comes from *At the River* (2016), Unit 1.

We begin with teaching the letters a, m, p, s, and t in both uppercase and lowercase. This lesson starts with letters, the smallest unit of meaning, and builds up to words, a larger unit of meaning. It can be used as an introductory literacy lesson on the first day of class or can be broken down into separate lessons for several hours or days. In our experience, we saw a class of low-literacy Spanish speakers master this lesson in 30 minutes, while a group of non-literate students who spoke non-Roman alphabet languages needed six hours of instruction to reach mastery.

The objectives of this lesson are:

- 1) to identify the letter name and sound for short Aa, Mm, Pp, Ss, Tt;
- 2) write the uppercase and lowercase forms of each;
- 3) connect the target sounds with whole words;
- 4) blend the sounds into CVC words; and
- 5) write the CVC words from dictation.

The lesson starts by presenting flashcards that display both the uppercase and lowercase forms of the letters as well as a picture of a keyword for each letter (for example, apple, /a/; map, /m/; pencil, /p/; sun,

/s/; table, /t/. The teacher begins by leading students in saying the letter name, the name of the item pictured, and the letter sound. Students repeat until each letter is mastered.

It is important to teach students that the uppercase form and lowercase forms both make the same sound. To illustrate, the teacher can point to the uppercase and lowercase letters, saying the same sound for each letter. Students are encouraged to repeat the letter sounds, the name of the item pictured, and the words “uppercase” and “lowercase.”

The next step is recognition of uppercase and lowercase letters while connecting them with the letter sounds. Displaying the five flash cards on the board, the teacher provides a simple matching exercise on the board: the five uppercase letters written in a column on the left, and the five lowercase letters written in a column on the right in a different order. Individual students volunteer to draw a line matching the two letters.

A	p
M	s
P	a
S	t
T	m

Another exercise to promote letter recognition is a letter scramble. The teacher writes several rows of lowercase letters, uppercase letters, or uppercase and lowercase letters mixed. Students chorally produce the sound as the teacher points to each letter. Examples of the three variations:

a	m	p	s	t	A	M	P	S	T	A	m	P	S	t
t	s	a	m	p	M	T	S	P	A	T	P	s	M	a
m	a	s	p	t	P	S	A	M	T	a	T	S	p	m

Once students are familiar with the sounds, they are ready to practice writing and connecting the sounds to whole words. The teacher shows students how to write each letter on a whiteboard or on paper.

Aa
Mm
Pp
Ss
Tt

For students who struggle to control the pencil or marker, the teacher can write the letters as a model and the student can copy. Or, the teacher can write the letters using a highlighter and the student can trace. Three-lined paper can be helpful when learning letter shapes as well. As each student finishes writing, the teacher asks him/her to produce the sound for each letter.

As students become comfortable with the sound and the two forms of each letter, they can participate in Whole Language Connection. As the teacher calls out words that begin with the target sounds, students move a small object like a bingo chip or paperclip on their written AMPST column to correspond to them. Words may include: Monday, Saturday, Tuesday, Sunday, paper, student, teacher, marker, pencil, apple, pen, mother, table, avenue, map, sister, ambulance. Students are encouraged to repeat the words several times as they move the chip to identify the initial sound.

Teachers can extend the Whole Language Connection by providing pictures and objects that begin with the target sounds. The visual support helps students connect with initial sounds, connect with whole words,

and learn new vocabulary. Additionally, the pictures and realia can be used for sorting activities and other games later in the lesson.

After students become comfortable recognizing beginning sounds, they are ready to be taught explicitly how sounds blend to form words. Using the target sounds only, the teacher presents visuals and realia for the decodable words *map*, *mat*, *sat*, *pat*, and *tap*. Students will receive oral language and visual support before trying to read the whole words themselves.

While displaying the visuals, the teacher encourages students to talk about them in any way that is useful to them. When showing a map, for example, teachers may find that students want to find their own country or countries they have visited. A student who spent 15 years in a refugee camp in Nepal enthusiastically shared a personal connection with a tap: she used to share one outdoor tap with three families, but now in the U.S., has three. When students are able to create connections between words and their lives, that meaning-making helps the language stick.

After spending sufficient time with the five new vocabulary words and their accompanying visuals, students are ready to blend the sounds they just learned into words. One effective technique is word building. First, the teacher writes *m*, *m*, *s*, *p*, and *t* (doubling the *m* is intentional) in a column on the board, points to each letter, and asks students for its letter sound. Next, the teacher adds *a* to each consonant and models blending the two sounds. The column now reads: *ma*, *ma*, *sa*, *pa*, *ta*. To elicit a single sound, the teacher taps under each letter; to indicate blending, the teacher runs a finger under the two letters, left to right. If students are fluently producing the two blended sounds, they are ready to add the last unit. The teacher adds *p*, *t*, *t*, and *p* to each word, making the column now read: *map*, *mat*, *sat*, *pat*, *tap*. Running a finger under the first two sounds, then tapping under the third, the teacher leads students in reading, *Ma...p*. *Ma...t*. *Sa...t*. *Pa...t*. *Ta...p*. Then, running a finger left to right under all three letters, the teacher models blending the whole word as students repeat. Constant reference to the pictures and realia ensures that phonics instruction is contextual, relevant, and easily understood.

Writing is the final step in this sequence. Students identify the picture or object as the teacher holds it up, then write the word on paper or a whiteboard. Consider this teacher's demonstration:

(Said while patting a student on the shoulder)

T: What am I doing?

Ss: Pat.

T: Yes, I can pat my friend's shoulder. Maybe she is sick. I can say, I hope you feel better. Pat, pat, pat. Please write pat. /P/.../a/.../t/. Pat.

Students should be encouraged to produce the sounds as they write. The teacher circulates, offering gentle corrections. For students who struggle to write the words, the teacher can write the word on their board for the students to copy. After going through each word and writing them down, students practice reading and pointing to the words in pairs.

This lesson allows students to learn the alphabetic principle of connecting letters and sounds through modeling, repetition, oral language, ample practice, and finally, reading and writing relevant words that are presented in context of daily life.

II. Decodable Words: CVC lesson

After students have mastered some letters and their sounds, they are able to participate in more complex decoding activities. This literacy lesson integrates oral language and phonics instruction through simple games and ample practice activities. Throughout the lesson, the teacher alternates top-down and bottom-up activities which give students practice in both oral language and direct phonics. Students achieve automaticity in decoding and blending nine single consonants and three short vowels which are presented contextually through objects that are relevant to daily life.

The teacher starts by reviewing the target sounds with flashcards: short vowels /a/, /i/, and /o/; consonants /b/, /d/, /g/, /m/, /n/, /p/, /r/, /t/, /x/. Cards should include a picture of the keyword plus the uppercase and lowercase form of each letter. After sound review, the targeted vocabulary is presented with realia: a map, a mat, a rag, a bag, a pad, a pan, a pin, a tin, a pot, a top, and a box. The students look at, hold,

and pass around the items as the teacher asks some discussion questions. Some example questions include: What is this? Do you have this at home? Do we have this in the classroom? What can you do with this?

When students are confident in saying the words and identifying the objects, the teacher writes the initial sounds in a column on the board: *m, m, r, b, p, p, p, t, p, t, b*. Students produce each sound as the teacher points to the letter. Next, the vowel sound is added (all vowels are short): *ma, ma, ra, ba, pa, pa, pi, ti, po, to, bo*. The teacher models blending the two sounds and leads the group in practicing the sounds in order.

When students are comfortably producing the blended sounds, the teacher adds the final sound and leads the group in blending the three sounds in order. To provide blending practice, the teacher can produce three separate sounds, tapping once for each sound or holding up one finger for each sound: “/b/.../a/.../g/.” Students listen and say the word “bag”. At this point, it may be helpful to lead students in segmenting as well: “Bag. What are the sounds in bag? /B/.../a/.../g/.” Students can tap or hold fingers up as they segment the word.

LESLLA students need ample practice as well as a variety of practice activities. One way to practice word recognition is to write all the vocabulary words on the board in random order and ask a volunteer to circle the word the teacher says. Students can help the volunteer by providing directions in English: up, down, left, right. This game continues until all of the words have been circled by different students. Another variation is to number the words 1-11 on the board. When the teacher says the word, the students say the corresponding number. Word cards provide yet another way to practice word recognition. Each student receives an index card with a vocabulary word written on it. Then students match the card to the correct item or picture on the table.

While phonics work is foundational for LESLLA learners, oral language development is also crucial. Games such as “What’s Missing?”, the Yes/No game, and TPR (Total Physical Response) provide students with opportunities to speak.

In What’s Missing? a volunteer closes his eyes while another student removes an object from the table. The volunteer opens his eyes and guesses the object that is missing. Classmates may help in English by giving prepositional hints (“next to the box”) or hints about the object’s purpose (“cooking” for pan or pot).

In the Yes/No game, the teacher holds up each object and makes a true/false statement about it: “This is a mat. Yes or no?” If it is a mat, the students say “yes.” If it is not, the students say “no” and provide the correct word. The teacher continues with all of the items. An effective TPR activity involves the teacher giving commands to a volunteer such as, “Put the top on the pot” or “Put the pad in the bag” while the student follows the instructions. More advanced students may volunteer to give the commands to another student. Alternating explicit phonics instruction with oral language activities provides the variety and the repetition that LESLLA students need to make the language comprehensible.

A culminating activity for this CVC lesson is simple dictation. The teacher holds up each item and elicits the name from the students, who are encouraged to repeat the word and segment the sounds as they write, for example: “Pad. /p/.../a/.../d/. Pad.” After students have written all eleven words, the teacher can lead a quick fluency exercise: The teacher says the words in random order while students circle the words on their whiteboard or paper. Then students can read the words individually for the teacher or a partner. Another extension is to use the Language Experience Approach, in which students dictate sentences about the objects to the teacher, who writes what they say on the board for later reading practice.

Because short vowels in English are often hard for learners to distinguish, ample practice is needed. Teachers may need to review and recycle using these practice activities in order to help students reach fluency and automaticity in decoding.

III. Initial Sounds and Word Recognition Using the *Basic Oxford Picture Dictionary*

How can you teach emergent readers who are successfully decoding *pan*, *box*, and *pin* to read words like *broccoli*, *spinach*, and *cucumber*? It is a significant sign of progress when LESLLA students are able to read decodable words, as illustrated in the previous two lessons. However, daily life also requires them to read words which contain a variety of sounds and spelling patterns which have not yet been explicitly taught, such as consonant blends, digraphs and long vowels. In the following technique, embedded in a “mainstream” ESL vocabulary lesson on vegetables, students use initial sounds and their knowledge of other single consonant sounds to help them recognize the names of vegetables in the *Basic Oxford Picture Dictionary*, 2nd edition. This

lesson can be used in a homogeneous or combination class of traditional ESL students and LESLLA students. The technique can be applied to any beginner vocabulary lesson.

After students warm up with a review of the consonant sounds /b/, /c/, /g/, /l/, /m/, /p/, /s/, /t/ that they will encounter in today's lesson, the teacher introduces the target vocabulary: broccoli, cabbage, lettuce, spinach, corn, garlic, string beans, tomato, pepper, cucumber, potato, onion, carrot, mushroom and peas. The introduction can be done through a variety of oral language activities: talking about pictures of the vegetables, passing around real or realistic vegetables, and asking questions such as, "Do you like ___?" or "Do you cook with _____?" Students may want to share the names of the vegetables in their L1, or talk about the ones they grew in their native country.

After students are comfortable saying the words, they are ready to connect oral language to print. The first step is to recognize each word's initial sound. The teacher displays the eight flashcards for b, c, g, l, m, p, s and t on the board and numbers them 1-8. A sample conversation could be:

(*Holding up a picture of a tomato*)

T: What is this?

Ss: Tomato.

T: What is the first sound in *tomato*?

Ss: /T/.

T: What number is the first sound?

Ss: Eight.

Continuing in this fashion, the students become aware of the connection between initial sound and letter for each vegetable. The teacher then refers students to the picture dictionary page that shows vegetable illustrations at the top and a list of words at the bottom. After several rounds of practice with the pictures and words on the page, the teacher writes 1-15 on the board along with the first sound of each vegetable, in the same order as in the book. Students produce the letter sound as the teacher points to each in order.

Next, students turn their attention away from the visuals and realia to the whole word. Referring to the pictures and/or the words in the book, students tell the teacher each word as he/she writes it on the board. The list looks like this:

broccoli	9. pepper
cabbage	10. cucumber
lettuce	11. potato
spinach	12. onion
corn	13. carrot
garlic	14. mushroom
string beans	15. peas
tomato	

First, the teacher asks students to repeat the words in order. Then, he/she asks, "What number is mushroom?" Some number of students will say, "Number 14." How did they know? They used their connection with the initial sound to scan the list and identify *mushroom* as number 14. The teacher continues to ask, "What number is lettuce? Garlic? Broccoli? Tomato?" Because there is only one item on the list with those initial sounds, students can identify those words easily using the initial sound strategy. As students identify the correct number, the teacher underlines the first sound.

This kind of list can also be used for further discrimination of sounds within the word. When the teacher asks, "What number is corn?", students using the initial sound strategy may answer with number 2, 5, 10, or 13. Imagine the following scenario:

T: What number is corn?

Ss: Number 13.

T: Ok, let's check number 13. (*running finger under each sound or syllable*): c...arr...ot. Carrot. Carrot. Is this corn?

Ss: No.

T: Ok, let's try again. What number is corn?

Ss: Number 2.

T: Let's check number 2. Ca...bb...age. Cabbage. Cabbage. Is this corn?

Ss: No.

T: What number is corn?

Ss: Number 5.

T: Let's check number 5. C...or...n. Is this corn?

Ss: Yes.

Using this process, students discover how to use the consonant sounds they already know to identify words. Recognition is a step on the road to independent reading. If the teacher uses this strategy consistently, then students will internalize it and apply it independently with new words. The initial sound strategy is an important scaffolding tool that builds strong connections for students with Roman alphabet letters and sounds.

IV. Scaffolded Reading with Comprehension Checking Questions

Once students are familiar with the alphabet and its sounds, decoding CVC words, and using initial sounds to recognize words, they can begin reading short passages. The following lesson is taken from the *Ventures Basic* (2010) health unit. Comprehension is emphasized first, so the teacher introduces the topic using plenty of oral language, pictures and realia. The teacher can act out the text or ask student volunteers to do so. Once students are familiar with the vocabulary, the teacher reads the text once or twice while the students listen. Afterwards, the teacher asks a series of yes/no comprehension check questions to make sure that the students understand the text. Then, the scaffolded reading of the text itself can begin. The ultimate goal is for the students to read the text on their own. The text is:

Tony and Mario are at the doctor's office. They are patients. Tony's leg hurts. His head hurts, too. Mario's arm hurts. His hands hurt, too. Tony and Mario are not happy. It is not a good day. (p. 50)

After reading the text twice, the teacher asks the students to respond *yes* or *no* to the following statements:

T: Tony and Mario are at the restaurant.

Ss: No.

T: Tony and Mario are at the post office.

Ss: No.

T: Tony and Mario are at the doctor's office.

Ss: Yes.

T: Tony and Mario are doctors.

Ss: No.

T: Tony and Mario are patients.

Ss: Yes.

The teacher continues in this fashion for the remainder of the text, checking comprehension.

Next, the teacher distributes the text to the students and asks them to follow along, either with their finger or their eyes, as he or she reads. After listening to the text several times and connecting the words to the print on the page, the students are ready to try echo reading. Here, the students repeat chunked passages after the teacher, chorally. Next, the students practice sentence recognition. The teacher shows the text, either written on the board or projected on a screen, with each sentence numbered 1-8. The teacher reads a sentence at random and asks the students to identify which number the sentence is. The students continue to call out the number of each sentence as they hear it.

As the students develop more confidence with the text, they can transition into sentence completion: reading the second half of the sentence after the teacher reads the first half. For example, the teacher reads,

“Tony and Mario . . .” and the students say, “. . . are at the doctor’s office.” As the students respond, the teacher can see which students are able to track with the words and which ones will need more practice. Other methods of practicing literacy with a whole text are:

1. *Reading in pairs*: Students read a sentence at a time with a partner as the teacher circulates and makes suggestions.
2. *Round robin reading*: Either in a small group or as a whole class, students read one sentence at a time.
3. *Sound identification*: The teacher makes the initial sound of a word from the text, such as short o. Looking at the text, students read a word from the text that has that sound (/o/...office). The teacher continues with 8-10 initial sounds from the text.
4. *Word identification*: Students dictate sentences to the teacher, who writes the sentences on the board. Students come to the board and circle the words/phrases the teacher or another student calls out. Or, students circle words on their paper that the teacher calls out.
5. *Sentence strips*: Students work in pairs or in groups to reorganize the text, which has been written on separate index cards, and put it back together in the correct order. This activity helps students with both word recognition and word order.

These activities are only a few of the methods teachers can use when helping LESLLA learners read beginner texts with better fluency and comprehension.

V. **Connecting Oral Language to Meaningful Print**

In this last lesson, students are exposed first to listening and speaking practice with whole sentences, which is then followed by scaffolded phonics, reading, and writing exercises. Offering ample speaking and listening practice before moving to print helps students learn new vocabulary and understand whole sentences.

The topic for this citizenship lesson is George Washington. The teacher begins by showing a picture of Washington and saying, “This is George Washington. He was the first American president.” Then, the teacher asks, “Who is this?” Students respond by saying “Washington” or “George Washington.” The teacher turns the one-word answer into a whole sentence: “Washington was the first president.” The class repeats the sentence. The teacher can ask again, “Who is this?” and cue the students to answer in a complete sentence.

The teacher continues by showing pictures or realia of a dollar bill, a quarter, a calendar of the month of February, and a map showing Washington D.C. The teacher models a complete sentence about each item, and cues students to repeat the full sentence, breaking it down into chunks as needed. The entire series is:

Washington was the first president.

Washington is on the dollar bill.

Washington is on the quarter.

Washington is the Father of Our Country.

Washington’s birthday is in February.

Washington, D.C. is the capital of the United States.

More or fewer sentences can be used, depending on the level of the students.

After the students have said the sentences several times, the teacher passes the pictures and realia one by one around the class. Each student holds an item, says the corresponding sentence, and passes it to the next student. That student repeats the sentence and passes the item to the next student, and so on until everyone has had a chance to say the sentence individually. This activity is repeated with all six sentences. The teacher should circulate the classroom to encourage each student to say the entire sentence correctly.

After discussing the pictures and realia, the teacher displays and reads the first sentence, which the students repeat. As the class practices, the teacher can use any of the guided/scaffolded reading strategies from the previous lesson to help students with fluency and oral/print connections.

After the students have read the sentences several times, they complete a dictation exercise, which can be differentiated according to each student’s level. Some students will only focus on a few initial sounds (/w/, /f/, /p/, /d/, /b/, etc.), while others will write entire missing words.

Another activity that involves the whole class is a sentence-scramble/line-up. Each student receives a card with a word from the sentence written on it, and must stand in front of the classroom in order, forming the entire sentence correctly. Individual or pair sentence scrambles give students the opportunity to use manipulatives as they practice word recognition techniques. Culminating activities include asking students to read the passage with a partner and individually for the teacher. Some students will enjoy reading out loud in front of the class.

This lesson provides multiple opportunities to interact with the text, which helps the students read independently and understand what they are reading. Ultimately, we want all students to become so familiar with a decoded text that they are able to demonstrate comprehension.

Conclusion

Our LESLLA students have taught us a great deal. We have come to recognize the crucial role of explicit phonics and literacy instruction in the ESL classroom. Teachers can meet the needs of all students by adapting traditional ESL approaches and adopting the balanced literacy approach. The lessons illustrated here have been effective with our classes, but teachers should alter them to best serve their particular groups of students. Our goal is clear: to integrate the best literacy practices with the best ESL practices so that all students, especially those with limited formal education, can acquire language and literacy for their lives in their new countries.

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